

Global Recognition of Palestinian Statehood: Problems and Prospects

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Abstract

Internationally, 144 of the 193 United Nations member states recognise a Palestinian state. On 28 May, two European Union (EU) members - Spain and Ireland - and non-EU Norway officially recognised a Palestinian state based on the 1949-67 borders. Ten of the EU's 27 member-states now recognise a Palestinian state. Those which so did prior to this month were Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czechia, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, and Sweden. Interestingly, in 2012, it was recognized as a state also by the UN General Assembly, but it failed to gain recognition as a full member state; It was therefore accorded a non-member observer state of the United Nations General Assembly. In order to become a full member state, Palestine needs the approval of at least two-thirds of the UN General Assembly's members and of at least nine of the 15 members of the UN Security Council, with no vetoes from the five permanent members, which is so far a very high hurdle. Recognition fulfils a long-held Palestinian aim and places additional pressure upon the Western powers who have all committed to the two-state solution for the Israeli-Palestinian conflict yet have done little to further it in the past few years. This study is an assessment of the modalities and tendencies towards the global recognition of the Palestinian state especially, as a move to the permanent solution to the Israeli-Hamas conflict. Hence, the researcher adopted the political realist theory. Meanwhile, data were collected through secondary means and subjected to interpretation by way of content analysis. Besides, the study, amongst others, recommends balance of power and complete exhaustion of all negotiation processes beyond existing substantive International law in relation with parties national interest.

Keywords: United Nations, International Law, Global Recognition of statehood, National interest, Conflict Resolution, Balfour agreement.

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Introduction

The global community has witness over the years the jostle and hustle surrounding the over hyped notion of declaration and as well recognition of Palestinian as a sovereign-state. Various existing literatures attempts to investigate, classify, clarify and interpret the legal and political standing for such moves. Nevertheless, little or nothing have been done to substantiate the political reality and implication of the Arab push for recognition of Palestinian statehood. Meanwhile, as the Palestinians' representatives began seeking support for international recognition for the state of Palestine, Israel reached out to other countries-most significantly, the United States-to block such a move. On December 15, 2010 the United States Congress passed a resolution condemning acts by the Palestinians to seek unilateral recognition of the state of Palestine. Suffice to say, Palestine needs the approval of at least two-thirds of the UN General Assembly's members and of at least nine of the 15 members of the UN Security Council, with no vetoes from the five permanent members, which is invariably a great limitation. As of today, the State of Palestine can sit as an observer at the UN General Assembly meetings but not vote.

However, the war that broke out on 7 October 2023 has changed dramatically Israel's international standing. The world is now more critical of Israel and more vocal in its support for Palestinian self-determination. It seems as if this can bring about the renewal of the Palestinian recognition momentum. Some Western European countries are already considering this as an option: Spain is one of them. For Israel, the recognition of the State of Palestine by friendly countries is very worrying.

The last thing this Israeli government wants to see is Palestinian statehood legitimized internationally (I would even say that for today's Israeli leadership this is no less than a nightmare). Levelling of Israel's and Palestine's legal status in the international arena –that is seen internationally as the gate to peace– is viewed in Israel as a diplomatic blow.

Theoretical Framework of Analysis

International relations represent a vast, multi-dimensional and evolving field of knowledge in an unprecedented way, especially in our time. Given that for every domain of knowledge (paradigm), it must have a theory or many theories to study, analyze and evaluate, and explain everything that surrounds it (Legro & Moravcsik, 1999).

The researcher adopted Realism or Realist Theory, which emerged as one of the most important theories in studying the field of international relations.

There is no doubt that the development of theory and the depth of theorizing together constitute the shortest path or the key to this science, because theory provides us with ways to systematize facts and simultaneously transform those facts into data and information, and then comes the other role of theory in how to select information and important useful data in the processes of description, classification, analysis, interpretation, and prediction (Faraj, 2007).

Prominent realist, Morgenthau believes that universal ethical principles cannot be applied to state affairs because morality in its form and its general and absolute content will not be appropriate for the implementation of political needs and in particular international relations. Thus, until these ethical principles become applicable, they must be revised to be valid and appropriate to the circumstances of the designated time and place.

National interest as a fundamental principle of realism at the level of international relations, projects that the world is a world of conflict and war because each country

has its own interests that seeks to achieve and which, at the same time, may be incompatible with the interests of other countries (Odeh, 2005).

Countries rationally and with interest, always make decisions that achieve their supreme national interest and always strive to enhance their capabilities to that end. All countries aim for this, even though they do not have complete and clear information that other opportunities exist (Ali, 2013).

However, Morgenthau cities in Odeh (2005), emphasizes that countries in order to address the international security dilemma must strive to change the patterns of their alliances to determine interest in the balance of power. In fact, the process of balance of power is not subject to any certain rules. Perhaps any system of balance of power could last for a long period, as it did with Britain during the 19th century, when it was controlling the balance of power in Europe. On the other hand, however, another system may continue for a short period, as it did in the 20th century after World War II, when the bipolar system, the multipolar system and then the unipolar system emerged after the collapse of the Soviet Union.

He (Morgenthau) believes that balance of power can be understood as a natural phenomenon in the lives of nations, international politics is nothing but a struggle for force, and balance of power is an inevitable consequence of this conflict. He also points out that a balance of power can be achieved in several ways such as divide and rule principle, compensation policy, armament policy and alliance system (Abu Khuzam, 2009).

In general, Interest is at the core of international politics. It is constant and is not affected by time or space conditions. However, interest in it's broad concept may include other variable parameters, which vary according to the political and cultural environment in which policies are created; General and inclusive moral principles cannot be applied to the actions of states, because these principles are different and diverse in its spatial and temporal condition. The Realist school of thoughts are always of the view that there are no absolute and universal values and principles. So it refuses to apply and

generalize the standards and aspirations that one people believes, to the rest of the peoples. Political realism focuses on the view that international relations are an autonomous domain, meaning that it is independent of other areas of knowledge such as economics, law and ethics (Morgenthau, 1964).

Historical Background of the Recognition of Palestinian Statehood

The '7 October War' is a strategic turning point for the Israeli-Palestinian bilateral relations, as well as for Israel's regional and global alliances. The concept marketed by the Israeli government that Hamas was contained and deterred, and that Israel could be integrated into the Middle East region without addressing the Palestinian issue –an idea that had been conveniently adopted by Western leaders– collapsed on that very day. In the midst of so much bloodshed and an enormous magnitude of destruction, talk of the need for a two-state solution has taken centre stage again. It is to be hoped that the international conversation on the 'day after' will dictate a strategic exit to this war that will bring about an Israeli-Palestinian peace agreement based on the two-states paradigm. A Spanish recognition of the State of Palestine at this stage can ignite the momentum that might lead to overall European and UN recognition.²

A. The People of Palestine and Eretz Israel

Prior to the British conquest and the assumption of the Palestine Mandate responsibilities, the territory was part of the Ottoman Empire. That Empire (although multiethnic) incorporated territories and populations of the MiddleEast that were largely -from a cultural point of view-Arabic.³

² Real Instituto elcano Royal Institute-9 April, 2024

³ Mim Kemal Oke, The Ottoman Empire, Zionism and the Question of Palestine, 14 INT'L J. MIDDLE EAST STuD. 329, 330 (1982).

Recent history of Palestine shows how Palestine has been under the control of various external forces; first subject to the force of invading conquerors and then the paternalistic caprice of colonial rule.⁴ Prior to WWII, the Palestinian territories were an international mandate under the authority of the League of Nations. Britain, which had conquered an occupied territory and displaced the Ottoman Empire, was granted the mandate to administer Palestine.⁵ This reflected the political reality that conquerors could retain their conquests subject to a weak form of international concern under the League's mandate system. One of the obligations of the mandatory power was to secure the well-being and interests of the people under its control and authority.

Making this international obligation more complex, Great Britain's Balfour Declaration articulated in 1917 prior to the end of the war-asserted British sympathies for Zionist ambitions in the Palestinian territories for Jewish immigration and settlement.⁶ In this sense, the Declaration was probably not consistent with the mandatory obligations of a Class A Mandate. British practices, which allowed significant Jewish immigration, had the consequence of creating a critical Jewish presence in Palestine, which eventually shaped future events. What is most salient during this period of recent history is the lack of promotion of self determination for the Palestinian residents by the UK. The defeat of the Ottoman Empire during the WWI meant that the conquering power had acquired temporary dominium over Palestine by conquest. The peace process created a new international institution, the 20th League of Nations.

⁴See NICHOLAS BETHELL, *THE PALESTINE TRIANGLE: THE STRUGGLE BETWEEN THE BRITISH, THE JEWS, AND THE ARABS, 1935-48* (1979) (discussing the recent occupiers of the territory)

⁵Brooks, *British Mandate for Palestine*, in 3 *THE ENCYCLOPEDIA OF THE ARAB-ISRAELI CONFLICT: A POLITICAL, SOCIAL, AND MILITARY HISTORY* 770 (Spencer C. Tucker ed., 2008).

⁶See generally JONATHAN SCHNEER, *THE BALFOUR DECLARATION: THE ORIGINS OF THE ARAB ISRAELI CONFLICT* (2010) (explaining the history of Britain's Balfour Declaration).

Under the Charter of the League a dispensation was made that the territories conquered by the conquerors would remain under their control, subject to a legal regime called the League of Nations Mandate System. The conquerors could keep the conquests, but mandate obligations required them to administer these territories in the interest of the inhabitants. Palestine was a Class A mandate.

This Class A mandate was somewhat distinctive in the sense that it contained a clause that was not expressed in Article 22 of the League Covenant. This clause involved the encouragement of Jewish immigration for the establishment of a natural home for the Jews who were a minority in Palestine. There was an ostensible incompatibility between the British Balfour Declaration for promoting immigration to Palestine and the requirements of Article 22.

B. The Recognition of the State of Israel

When Britain, the mandatory power, requested in 1947 that the United Nations consider the future dispensation for the territory defined within the Palestinian Mandate, the U.N. General Assembly created a special committee to investigate the international legal status of the Palestinian territory.⁷ The committee determined that the British Mandate should be terminated and that independence should be granted to Palestine at the earliest possible time.⁸ Despite the recommendation of "independence" and the committee's majority view that Palestine was to be partitioned into an Arab state and a Jewish state, the committee stipulated that the territory's Arab and Jewish communities were to be linked in an economic association. The status of Jerusalem, it was recommended, should be a separate entity under international supervision. The U.N. General Assembly, after lengthy debate, decided with more than 2/3 of a majority to accept the partition recommendations.

⁷G.A. Res. 106(S-1), para. 1, U.N. Doc. A/RES/106(S-1) (May 15, 1947).

⁸Rep. to GOAR, UN. Spec. Commn on Palestine 2d Sess., Sept. 3, 1947, para. 1, U.N.Doc. A/364 (1947).

C. Palestinian Statehood and the United Nations Mandate

The criteria of statehood that requires a body politic is generally known as a population. The population issue in Palestine has been contentious since the initiation of the Class A mandate. The mandate recognized a population of Palestinians under Article 22 of the league mandate. This recognition was influenced by the mandate's purpose to secure the population's right to self-determination. However, Britain, the mandatory power, announced a policy for Palestine to secure a homeland in Eretz Israel for the Jewish people in the Diaspora, prior to assuming mandate responsibilities. This was expressed in the Balfour Declaration.

Balfour, in confidence, expressed the view to the British Prime Minister that the major purpose of Article 22, namely the self-determination for Palestinian inhabitants, could not be implemented because of the undertaking to promote a Jewish homeland in Palestinian territory. As it turned out, because Britain was not able to emerge with a successful solution to this problem, it passed the matter on to the U.N. General Assembly. Article 22, which juridically established a right of self-determination for the Palestinians, was left unimplemented. The critical question is how much of this right has survived to strengthen the claim to statehood under international law for the people of Palestine. To the extent that the government of Israel may provide some impediments to the realization of statehood, international law may support a weakening of the Israeli position.

CONTENDING ISSUES/ PROBLEMS

A. Criteria of Statehood

The accepted criteria of statehood were laid down in the Montevideo Convention (1933), which provided that a state must possess a permanent population, a defined territory, a government, and the capacity to conduct international relations.

i. Permanent Population

Recognition of Statehood requires there should be a permanent (Palestinian) population. There is a permanent Palestinian population in the West Bank and Gaza. What makes a final settlement complex is that there are now millions of (absentee) Palestinians whose citizenship rights were abrogated by Israeli legislation and administrative measures. Obviously at a minimum, there is a Palestinian population inside the territories occupied by Israel that qualifies as a permanent population.

One factor that has influenced Israeli perspectives is the claim that the Palestinians are not a people for the purpose of the population requirement of statehood. The evidence from careful research demonstrates a continuity of Palestinian national identity. Israel has promoted the argument that Palestinians are simply Arabs and therefore, indistinguishable from other Arabs in surrounding states. Some Arab nationalists have in fact supported this view in the early efforts to create a Pan-Arab Union. The strength of nation-state national identity proved too strong for this innovation. It therefore becomes important to state that Palestinians are a national body politic, with strong national identity, and with an identity that is continuous, particularly during the period of the U.N. Mandate and under the U.N. Charter framework.

ii. Defined Territory

Another criterion is that the body politic must be territorially determined or determinable.

It is worthy to state that boundaries indicated in relevant U.N. Security Council resolutions established conditions which are determined or determinable. There exist factors in the context which suggest that Israel, a key negotiator and player may have broader territorial ambitions and this may be at the expense of Palestinian statehood. A justification for Israeli territorial concerns has been suggested by Prime Minister Netanyahu in his speech before the U.N. on September 23, 2011.

Essentially, Netanyahu insists that because of the diminutive territorial status of Israel and a period of fifty years of war and insurrection, Israel has some implicit claims to territorial enhancement to ensure a higher level of security for the state. That is the Realist practical issue. The Prime Minister noted that many states entertain a military presence in other states for mutual security purposes; for example, France in Africa and the United States in Europe and Japan. It is possible that the Prime Minister is also influenced by the realism of the restoration of the historic boundaries of ancient Israel, the Eretz Israel boundaries. One pressing issue is the dynamism of territories and the requirement under Montevideo state qualifications that, if there is to be a Palestinian state, this state has to have agreed-upon boundaries that provide a viable territorial base for a state. The apparently interminable negotiations also formed a basis by which Israel can change the facts regarding the appropriate reach of territory that may fall within any settlement.

Essentially, one of the ways that the territorial question can be effectually pre-determined prior to negotiation is by a continuation and expansion of the Israeli settlement program.

Politically, the expansion of settlements is a cornerstone of the ultra-nationalist program and policy in Israel. This policy goes forward amidst a propaganda campaign that insists only the Israelis make concessions and that the Palestinians "take and take." It is worth a reminder that the Oslo Accords, in which Peres was a key player, involved Arafat giving up on the 1947 U.N. boundaries for the one defined in 1967. In doing so, Arafat gave up 22% of the historic Palestine; and Israel enlarged its territory on

the historic Palestine from owning 56% to owning 78%. The Obama Administration insisted on a freeze on settlement building projects on Palestinian land. Netanyahu agreed to a ten-month freeze in order to encourage the initiation of talks.

However, during these ten months construction was the same as in the previous ten months. The Obama Administration has pressed Netanyahu to give another two months for the freeze. The U.S. administration has had no influence on Netanyahu's settlement policies. Moreover, the American administration's position is weakened by the pressure of the American pro-Israel lobby. Why is Netanyahu reluctant to stop the settlement expansion? The longer it continues, the more intractable the foundation of a viable peace becomes. In fact, the settlement strategy may be meant to be a deal breaker. Why would Netanyahu be interested in telling the United States he supports a settlement to the conflict while his activities and behavior all point in the direction of a strategy designed to continue fighting indefinitely with no final conclusion, except one that is created on the ground? Settlements are creating and contain the capacity for re-writing the map, making it impossible for future Israeli authorities to undo the map. Netanyahu has refused to give any assurance about the settlement freeze. Netanyahu rules with a complex coalition of ultra-nationalist interests.

Interestingly, the only legitimate boundaries of the state of Israel, according to them, are not defined by international law but by the history and antiquity of Jewish culture. This point was also stressed by Balfour. The historical boundaries of Israel, therefore, include Ancient Sumeria and Judea.

In short, the only acceptable boundaries are those of Eretz Israel (a greater Israel). In this Israel, there is no room for Palestinians. The boundaries of greater Israel direct us to another principle: the idea that there will never be a Palestinian state. It has long

been accepted in ultra-nationalist circles that the Palestinians are not a real national entity or people and thus, as the argument goes, the Palestinians may not claim on the basis of national identity that they are people qualified to carry the mantle of statehood. When we come to the question of the governance of the Palestinian entity, this represents a more complex issue. Under the Oslo Accords, a Palestinian National Authority was set up.

The agreement left final status issues as matters to be negotiated between Israel and the PNA. This implicitly left the PNA with a certain measure of internal autonomy, and some measure of external competence, but the Oslo Accords suggest that final status includes Palestinian statehood. This understanding carries the assumption that the PNA does not claim full sovereign independent status since the status must be negotiated with Israel. Clearly, to establish a promising claim for statehood the Palestinians would have to repudiate any understanding that statehood is conditioned by an Israeli veto. The veto would not be exercised in any formal sense. It could be reflected simply in a strategy that is unwilling or reluctant to achieve a settlement. In this sense, if Palestinian statehood is tied to the conclusion of an agreement with Israel, and Israelis are reluctant to conclude, their conduct amounts to a veto if it is also claimed that statehood cannot be considered by the U.N. or the international community unless there is an Israeli agreement. The strategy of seeking recognition of statehood must address this question as well.

More so, it could be argued that Resolution 181 at least implies the idea that international law supports the notion of "an Arab state" as part of the Partition Plan. It could also be argued that the Security Council resolutions recognizing the West Bank and Gaza as Palestinian territories are de jure recognition that the boundaries of the Palestinian people are determinable and that the U.N. Security Council resolutions provide the baseline for determining the boundaries. These resolutions form the foundation of negotiations relating to the Oslo Accords, which essentially involved an

acceptance by the parties of these boundaries. This means that Palestinians have already conceded a huge portion of Palestinian land to Israel to secure agreement to settlement.

iii. A Functioning Government

This issue is somewhat more problematic, because the Palestinian Authority (PA) was created as an interim entity and not a permanent governing authority. Here, the Palestinians, by drafting a valid constitution and creating a government under that constitution, could meet the criteria of statehood unambiguously. The PNA does meet some of the criteria relating to the capacity to enter into relations with other states. The degree of recognition that Palestinian entities have received suggests that the Palestinian leadership is capable of discharging these obligations.

The PNA has relations with at least 140 other states that could qualify as meeting the minimum requirements of diplomacy. Additionally, the observer status of the PLO at the U.N. and the degree of the PNA and the PLO's participation in international organizations, enhances the claim that a future government has the capacity to enter into relations with other states and entities in the international environment. These are the conditions indicated in the Montevideo Convention on the Rights and Duties of States.

Since the adoption of the U.N. Charter, there has been a modest change in the notion of sovereignty as the criterion of the legal personality of the state. That change requires that a state as a sovereign entity is able and willing to accept the rights, as well as the obligations, of a state under the charter of the United Nations. Since this would include the fundamental purpose and values behind the U.N. Charter, it would be appropriate that the constitution of a Palestinian state and its practices reflect on issues of international peace and security, commitment to the rule of law, a commitment to fundamental human rights, and a commitment to global security and democracy.

These latter conditions are ones that bring an element of "authority" to the expression of sovereignty. It could be argued that Israeli sovereignty is somewhat diminished by its unwillingness to adopt the constitutional guidelines of Resolution 181. It has been commonly assumed that Resolution 181 provided the international legal imprimatur for the creation of the Israeli state and an Arab state. Resolution 181 contained certain guidelines as to what the political structure of rights and duties of the future states should encompass. The Israeli leadership took the green light of the Resolution 181 and declared its independence. The Declaration was a document that complied fully with the guidelines of Resolution 181. However, although there was an intent that the Declaration should be the inspiration for the new Israeli Constitution, such a Constitution did not emerge. This means that Israel effectually refused to adopt its own declaration of independence as containing legally binding prescriptive norms. In this sense, Israeli objections to Palestinian statehood would appear to be objections to the mandate of international law itself. In reality, the only stumbling block on the pathway to the recognition of Palestinian statehood would be the United States exercising a veto over the process in the Security Council. This would be an ill-advised vote, however, it is one that the Palestinians must strategically seek to overcome or minimize through the use of international provisions such as "Uniting for Peace". Currently, there are more or less 114 countries that already recognize Palestinian statehood. Such recognition is in the first instance a matter of state sovereignty exercised bilaterally. The nature of these agreements gives an advantage to the Palestinians for them to try to secure an overwhelming bilateral commitment for a recognition of Palestinian sovereignty. Already, important Latin American states have given their commitments.

Additionally, it could also be advantageous for Palestinians to seek recognition of their statehood in regional international organizations such as the League of Arab States, the African Union, OAS, European Union etc. Regional recognition would be politically efficient for the Palestinians to develop their constitution and constitute their government. With this background, it may be vastly more difficult for the United States to exercise a veto in the face of an overwhelming global consensus. It would seem to be

clear that the recognition of Palestinian statehood must meet the Montevideo criteria of statehood and more under the U.N. Charter.

It must be noted that Montevideo was modified by post World War II developments regarding the criteria of statehood in international law. The first issue is the recognition of their claims to territory. First, U.N. General Assembly Resolution 181 develops the partition of land. The boundaries indicated in that resolution were the boundaries adopted by Israel to define its territorial space. Since the Palestinians were not an organized entity at that time, they were not in a position to either adopt the U.N. partition scheme or even to repudiate it.

Nevertheless, it is worth noting that, as earlier discussed, Israel's boundaries were partially defined and Palestinian boundaries were determinable in this sense. These determinable boundaries would meet the criterion of territoriality for State recognition. After the 1967 war, Israel occupied Gaza and the West Bank. It still occupies those territories. However, Israel has agreed to Resolutions 242 and 338; and the Palestinians have agreed to the territorial dispensation indicated in these resolutions. This means that Palestinians, in effect, accept less territory than originally envisioned in Resolution 181. Boundaries may be redefined by agreement; not merely through military action. As most developing world militaries are mainly concerned with internal security (national interest) that implies in future military officers throughout the world will be more interested in politics and government, (Jaja, 2024).

This means that Israel (national interest) needs an agreement that will accommodate its settlement activity in Palestinian territory. In short, settlement activity flies in the face of U.N. Resolutions 242 and 338, and is therefore unlawful. Here the lawfulness of the boundaries under these resolutions is grounded in the Security Council's competence to make binding international law. The unlawfulness can be cured by an agreement between Israel and the Palestinians. For such an agreement or understanding to have legal efficacy, it would probably have to be sanctioned or approved by the Security

Council.

One final point-the matter that does not make it into the front lines of negotiation-is the deep belief of Israeli ultra-nationalists that international law boundaries in the context of this conflict are not legitimate. They use the legitimate boundaries of Israel as defined by ancient history, in which the ancient state of Israel was sovereign over lands, now claimed to be Palestinian. This is a deeply held belief; and it may well be that, so long as the extreme ideology of ultra-nationalism controls the government of Israel, there will be no final settlement that involves territorial determinations incompatible with the Eretz Israel idea.

The next element of statehood is the element of governance. It would seem that the agreement to create the PA with a degree of internal autonomy goes a long way toward the requirement that there be a discernible form of governance with lines of authority. However, it has been clearly understood that the PA is not really meant to be a governing body in an international sense. This means that the PLO and its allies must reconstitute the PNA in the form of a recognizable government, with a working draft constitution, and with a framework of transparency, responsibility, and accountability. It would also be appropriate that such an organization draft a constitution that approximates international standards in order to show that the Palestinian governing authority is willing, ready, and able to meet its international responsibilities under the U.N. Charter. It bears notice that the U.N. partition plan stipulated that the constitutions of both Arab and Jewish states would guarantee "all persons equal and nondiscriminatory rights in civil, political, economic and religious matters and the enjoyment of human rights and fundamental freedoms, including freedom of religion, language, speech and publication, education, assembly and association.

The declaration of the establishment of Israel indicated that the new state "will uphold the full social and political equality of all its citizens without distinction of religion, race,

or sex." After this promising start, the declaration was never adopted by the Knesset; and no efforts were made to draft a constitution along these lines. However, both Israelis and Palestinians would have benefited by establishing the Israel with a constitution based on this declaration. It should be noted that the Knesset delegated the task of drafting a constitution to its Constitution, Law, and Justice Committee, which has never presented the Knesset with a draft constitution.

PROSPECTS

The war that broke out on 7 October 2023 has changed dramatically Israel's international standing. The world is now more critical of Israel and more vocal in its support for Palestinian self-determination. It seems as if this can bring about the renewal of the Palestinian recognition momentum. Some Western European countries are already considering this as an option following the recognition by Spain which is predicted to pull a band wagon effect in the international community. For Israel, the recognition of the State of Palestine by friendly countries is very worrying.

The last thing this Israeli government wants to see is Palestinian statehood legitimized internationally (I would even say that for today's Israeli leadership this is no less than a nightmare). The levelling of Israel's and Palestine's legal status in the international arena –that is seen internationally as the gate to peace– is viewed in Israel as a diplomatic blow.

A Spanish recognition of Palestine at this stage can ignite the momentum that might lead to overall European and UN recognition. Her announcement could again raise the prospect that the EU, as a bloc, will recognize an independent Palestine. Spain's Prime Minister, Pedro Sánchez, recently announced his intention of recognizing the State of Palestine earlier 2024 and has done that to throw her weight in support Palestinian full

membership of the UN. Needless to say, Spain would become a meaningful player towards a new diplomatic momentum on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, in line with its previous effort when it hosted the Madrid Peace Conference on the Middle East in 1991.

Another, though smaller, worry for the Israeli government at the moment are the sanctions imposed on extremist Israeli settlers who have violently attacked or committed human rights abuses against Palestinians in the West Bank. In Israel, this is considered to be related to the issue of Palestinian recognition. Leaders of the Israeli settlers are seen by the nationalistic part of the Israeli society as its modern pioneers –in other words, as its national heroes–. Restrictions on traveling to friendly countries or on the ability to register bank accounts by prominent settlers are seen as an international de-legitimation of the settlements and of Israel's control of the West Bank as a whole. Six countries have already taken such measures recently: the US, the UK, Canada, France, New Zealand and Spain. Also, the EU reached a political agreement in March to sanction extremist Israeli settlers.

However, it is hard to tell if this is a beginning of a new international trend, but if it is, it might push forward the Western tendencies in favour of the recognition of Palestine.

The aftermath of the recognition of Palestinian statehood by Spain and Ireland in all indication spur Belgium, Luxembourg, Malta, and Slovenia probably to be the next EU member-states to follow suit. These four countries doing so would result in over half of the EU's members recognising a Palestinian state.

Given the EU effect to recognition of Palestinian statehood, Israeli's willful act of relinquishing their position on Palestinian sovereignty becomes over heated and impossible. While speaking to TNA, Matthew Bryza, the former US deputy assistant secretary of state for Europe and Eurasia, said that more EU member-states recognising the State of Palestine will not impact the Israeli military attack on Rafah. Given that

Netanyahu is moving ahead with this incursion regardless of what the US thinks - and considering that Washington has far more leverage over Tel Aviv than any European capitals do - it would be difficult to argue that countries like Spain, Ireland, and Norway recognising a Palestinian state would impact Israeli actions in Rafah at this point. "Prime Minister Netanyahu has made it absolutely clear that come hell or high water the IDF is going to continue its offensive on Rafah," explained Bryza.

Conclusion

The events of 7 October and those that followed exposed how irresponsible it was for the international community to neglect one of the most dangerous and volatile conflict areas on earth. The war that broke out that day has changed dramatically Israel's international standing. The world is now more critical of Israel and more vocal in its support for Palestinian self-determination. It seems as if this can bring about the renewal of the momentum for Palestinian recognition. Some Western European countries are sequentially considering this an option, Spain among them. The Gaza war should be brought to a halt in the shortest time possible. It should be the last war ever fought between Israel and the Palestinians. To this end, the aim of any peace agreement must be strategic coexistence between the parties, in line with all relevant UN resolutions.

Recommendations

On the basis of above analyses, the following recommendations were made;

First, unilateral recognition of Palestinian Statehood at the UN would be a major setback for peace. UN endorsement of a unilaterally declared Palestinian state at this time, after Hamas' massacre of more than 1,200 Israelis on October 7, would be perceived as a huge victory for this Iran-backed terrorist organization, sending a signal to militant extremists and belligerent states around the world to follow suit.

Second, recognition of such a state and its admission to the UN will undermine any efforts to resume negotiations between Israelis and Palestinians. It will reward Palestinians who believe they can rely solely on international pressure on Israel rather than make the necessary compromises for peace.

Third, the Palestinian Authority does not satisfy the traditional criteria for statehood, including control over defined territory, a permanent population, and an effective government. The war between Israel and Hamas underscores that the Palestinian Authority does not control the Gaza Strip, although Gaza is considered part of the purported Palestinian state. The PA's inability to rein in Hamas violates a fundamental attribute of any effective government: monopoly over the use of force. Likewise, with some Palestinian voices accepting two states whose territorial boundaries will be negotiated with Israel, others declare that all of the land between the river and the sea is Palestine.

Fourth, unilateral Palestinian attempts to acquire attributes of statehood outside the negotiating process violate existing Israeli-Palestinian agreements, which clearly state that permanent status issues are subject to agreement between the parties. These same agreements are the legal basis for the existence of the Palestinian Authority. Seemingly, undermining the contours of those agreements will dissolve the PA.

Fifth, only through direct negotiations with Israel can the Palestinians fully realize their national aspirations. Any attempted shortcut, either at the UN or elsewhere, will only delay a solution, thus unnecessarily prolonging the suffering of both Israelis and Palestinians.

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